

Synthesis of Fural Analogs of Substituted Flavonoids

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Synthesis of furyl analogs of methyl and halogeno substituted flavonoids is described. Antimicrobial activity of these compounds is studied.

FLAVONOIDS having heterocyclic nucleus in place of one of the phenyl nucleus were claimed to possess biological activity. Coronary dialatory activity^{1,2,10} muscular relaxation effect³, spasmolytic activity^{1,4,5}, anticancer activity⁶, and antimicrobial activity⁷⁻⁹, are claimed to have been associated with heteroanalogs of flavonoids. Methyl and halogeno groups are known to have activity enhancing effect. In view of these aforesaid studies, it was thought worth to synthesise furyl analogs of methyl and halogeno substituted flavonoids and study their biological activity.

Two different routes were followed for the synthesis of these flavonoids (Fig. 1). 2-(2-Furoyl)-2'-hydroxyacetophenones (II, 1-11, Table 1) were prepared by Baker-Venkataraman method¹¹, 3-(2-furyl)-2'-

of 2-(2-furyl)-chromones prepared by two different methods, served as an unambiguous proof in support of the structures of 2-(2-furoyl)-2'-hydroxyacetophenones, 3-(2-furyl)2'-hydroxy-acrylophenones and 2-(2-furyl)-chromones proper. 3-(2-Furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenones were also cyclised to 2-(2-furyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones (VI, 1-11, Table 1)

Antimicrobial activity :

These compounds were subjected to in vitro activity testing against various pathogenic bacteria and fungi. Most of the compounds did not show any promising activity. Results of activity testing of those compounds which showed some activity are summarised in Table 2.

Fig. 1.

hydroxy-acrylophenones (V, 1-11, Table 1) were prepared by the condensation of substituted acetophenones (I) with furan-2-aldehyde and 2-(2-furyl) chromones (IV, 1-10, Table 1) by the cyclization of both 2-(2-furoyl)-2'-hydroxyacetophenone and 3-(2-furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenone. The identity

Experimental

2'-Furoxy acetophenones (II, 1-11, Table 1) :

Furoyl chloride (0.022 mol) was added to the solution of 2'-hydroxy acetophenones (I) (0.02 mol) in anhydrous pyridine. Reaction mixture was

TABLE I. DESCRIPTION OF FUROXY ACETOPHENONES, AND FURYL ANALOGS AT FLAVONOIDS
(Nomenclature according to chemical abstract, micro-analysis results not given, % of constituent elements was found to be in good agreement with calculated values).

Group	Compound No.	Substituent			Nature	Crystallisation Solvent	Yield % (approx.)	M.P. °C
		R'	R''	R'''				
2'-(2-Furoxy)-acetophenone	II-1	H	H	CH ₃	Liquid	—	—	—
	II-2	H	H	Cl	Colourless needles	Ethanol	33	105
	II-3	H	H	Br	"	"	42	134
	II-4	H	CH ₃	H	Liquid	—	—	—
	II-5	H	Cl	H	Colourless needles	Ethanol	33	125
	II-6	H	Br	H	"	"	50	120
	II-7	H	I	H	"	"	50	112
	II-8	CH ₃	H	H	"	"	30	85
	II-9	Cl	H	H	"	"	50	85
	II-10	Br	H	H	"	"	40	94
	II-11	I	H	H	"	"	40	98
3-(2-Furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.	III-1	H	H	CH ₃	Yellow needles	60% methanol	40	95
	III-2	H	H	Cl	Colourless needles	60% acetone	40	58
	III-3	H	H	Br	"	50% ethanol	25	55
	III-4	H	CH ₃	H	Liquid	—	—	—
	III-5	H	Cl	H	Colourless needles	Ethanol	53	77
	III-6	H	Br	H	"	60% acetone	40	145
	III-7	H	I	H	Yellow needles	70% acetic acid	40	150
	III-8	CH ₃	H	H	"	60% ethanol	80	77
	III-9	Cl	H	H	"	"	72	119
	III-10	Br	H	H	"	Methanol	50	134
	III-11	I	H	H	"	Ethanol	60	154
2-(2-Furyl)-chromone	IV-1	H	H	CH ₃	Colourless needles	60% methanol	50	148
	IV-2	H	CH ₃	H	Pink needles	60% ethanol	50	130
	IV-3	H	Cl	H	Colourless needles	"	50	208
	IV-4	H	Br	H	"	"	80	210
	IV-5	H	I	H	"	50% methanol	40	187
	IV-6	CH ₃	H	H	"	Ethanol	60	165
	IV-7	Cl	H	H	"	"	71	214
	IV-8	Br	H	H	"	"	66	217
	IV-9	I	H	H	Pink needles	"	80	199
3-(2-Furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenone	V-1	H	H	CH ₃	Yellow needles	Ethanol	32	62
	V-2	H	H	Cl	Grey needles	"	33	108
	V-3	H	H	Br	Yellow needles	"	58	155
	V-4	H	CH ₃	H	"	50% ethanol	41	58
	V-5	H	Cl	H	"	Ethanol	47	113
	V-6	H	Br	H	"	"	50	92
	V-7	H	I	H	"	90% methanol	61	90
	V-8	CH ₃	H	H	"	Ethanol	40	54
	V-9	Cl	H	H	"	"	45	85
	V-10	Br	H	H	"	"	50	102
	V-11	I	H	H	"	"	55	125
2-(2-Furyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone	VI-1	H	H	CH ₃	"	70% ethanol	60	189 (152)
	VI-2	H	H	Cl	"	"	53	227 (185)
	VI-3	H	H	Br	Brownish needles	Ethanol	40	208 (178)
	VI-4	H	CH ₃	H	Yellow needles	"	54	193 (148)
	VI-5	H	Cl	H	"	"	60	215 (192)
	VI-6	H	Br	H	"	"	55	210 (191)
	VI-7	H	I	H	"	"	58	195 (210)
	VI-8	CH ₃	H	H	"	"	53	198 (145)
	VI-9	Cl	H	H	"	"	50	168 (149)
	VI-10	Br	H	H	"	"	55	218 (197)
	VI-11	I	H	H	"	"	58	206 (215)

Note :—M.P. brackets refer to the m.p. of acetates of corresponding 2-(2-Furyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.

TABLE 2. RESULTS OF ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY TESTING (*in vitro*). FIGURES INDICATE THE CONCENTRATION IN $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. AT WHICH THE GROWTH WAS INHIBITED

Compound No.	S. Faecalis	S. Aureus (R)	S. Aureus (S)	K. Pheumoniae	Ps. Aeruginosa	F. Coli	S. Typhimurium	T. Monta	Myc. Smegmatis	C. Albicans	B. Subtilis
II-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	200	-	-	-
II-11	-	-	200	-	-	-	-	200	200	200	-
III-1	-	-	200	-	-	-	-	50	50	50	50
III-8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	50	50	-
III-9	-	200	-	-	-	-	-	12	12	200	12
III-6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	200	200	200	200
III-10	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	12	-	12
III-7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	200	200	200	-
III-11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	50	-	-
IV-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	200	-	-
V-2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	200	200	-	-
V-1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	-	50

Compound No.	Tricho. Foetus	Fus. Osy. sporium	P. Citrinium	A. Niger	C. Neoformans	H. Cap-sulatum	B. Dermati-tidis	Kantho-monas. V.	S. Pyo-genes	Soum-Lantae	M. Tuber-culosis H.37 RV
II-10	-	-	200	200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
II-11	-	-	200	200	200	-	-	-	-	-	-
III-1	-	-	200	200	200	-	-	-	12	200	25
III-8	-	-	50	-	50	-	-	-	50	-	-
III-9	-	-	200	-	200	-	-	-	12	12	-
III-6	-	-	200	-	200	-	200	200	50	200	-
III-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	12	-
III-7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	200	200	-
III-11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	50	-
IV-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	25
V-2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
V-1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	-	-

stirred and was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hr. It was then poured over ice cooled 10% hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was filtered, washed successively with water, 2% sodium hydroxide and finally with water. Compounds were further purified by crystallization. Compound No. II-1 and 4 were liquid and were isolated by ether extraction of the reaction mixture after it was poured in ice cooled hydrochloric acid. Compounds decomposed on heating and, therefore, b.p. could not be recorded.

2-(2-Furoyl)-2'-hydroxy-acetophenones (III, 1-11, Table 1) :

2'-Furoxy-acetophenone (0.02 mol) was dissolved in anhydrous pyridine (10 ml) and powdered potassium hydroxide (0.02 mol) was added to it. After stirring for about 10 min, reaction mixture solidified to a yellow mass. The yellow solid was decomposed by dil. acetic acid to an oil which soon solidified. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised.

Compound III.4 was liquid and was isolated by ether extraction of acetic acid decomposed reaction mixture. Because of heat sensitive nature B.P. could not be recorded.

2-(2-Furyl)-Chromones : (IV, 1-9, Table 1) :

A mixture of 2-(2-Furoyl)-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone (0.002 mol), glacial acetic acid (10ml) and concentrated

hydrochloric acid (1 drop), was refluxed for 15 min. It was then poured over crushed ice and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with 2% sodium hydroxide and finally with water. Compounds were further purified by crystallisation.

3-(2-Furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenones : (V, 1-11, Table 1) :

To the solution of 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone (I) (0.01 mol) and furan-2-aldehyde (0.1 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added aqueous potassium hydroxide (20%, 10 ml) and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. The yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and purified by crystallisation.

2-(2-Furyl)-Chromones : (IV, 1-9, Table 1) :

A mixture of 3-(2-furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenone (0.02 mol), equal amount by weight of selenium dioxide and amylalcohol (20 ml) was refluxed at 150° for 15 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and filtered to remove precipitated selenium. The filtrate was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and steam distilled to remove amyl alcohol. The contents of distillation flask were cooled and extracted with ether. The ether was evaporated and the solid obtained was purified by crystallisation.

2-(2-Furyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones (VI, 1-11, Table 1) :

-2-(2-Furyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenone (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) and to the resulting solution was added aqueous sodium hydroxide (20%, 10 ml) and hydrogen peroxide (20 vol, 20 ml). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 6 hr. It was then diluted with water and acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. Solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and purified by crystallisation.

2-(2-Furyl)-3-acetoxy-chromone (VII, Fig. 1) :

To the solution of -2-(2-furyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone (0.002 mol) in minimum quantity of dry pyridine, was added acetic anhydride (2 drops). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. The crystalline solid obtained was filtered, washed rapidly with 1 ml of ethanol and dried. (Compounds were found to be very pure, no further purification needed).

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References

1. G. JONGENBREUN, *Pharm. Weekblad.*, 1951, **86**, 661. *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, **47**, 2172.
2. J. SCHMUTZ, R. HIRT, F. KUNZLE, E. EICHENBENGER and H. LAUENER, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1953, **36**, 620.
3. J. KOO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **36**, 635.
4. G. JONBEGREUR, *Arch. Intern. Pharmacodynamic.*, 1950, **90**, 384. *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, **47**, 760.
5. M. M. BAGOUNI, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1949, **1**, 177. *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, **43**, 5542.
6. D. DONNALLY, R. GROGHEGEN, C. O'BRIEN, E. PHILIBIN, R. GAN and T. S. WHEELER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 872. *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, **64**, 4127.
7. W. B. GIGER and J. E. CENN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 112.
8. D. H. MARRIAN, P. B. RUSSEL and A. R. TODD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1419.
9. S. C. KUSHWAHA, DINKER and J. B. LAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 82.
10. J. KOO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, **53**, 1329. *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **62**, 6455.
11. W. D. OLLIS and D. WEIGHT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3825.